

PSYCHOLOGICAL DEPENDENCE ON TOBACCO PRODUCTS AND THEIR EFFECT ON THE HUMAN BODY

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Annotation: The transmission of signals between brain cells occurs with the help of neurotransmitters. These are biologically active substances that are produced by neurons and some organs of the endocrine system. Nicotine is structurally similar to the neurotransmitter acetylcholine. Therefore, nerve cells actively capture it with the help of receptors. In response to nicotine stimulation, neurons increase the release of dopamine, the hormone of happiness and euphoria. At the same time, the concentration of adrenaline, norepinephrine, cortisol – hormones involved in stress reactions - increases in the blood.

Keywords: quit smoking, smoked cigarettes, blood pressure

A cascade of biochemical reactions leads to the appearance of signs of smoking. A person feels a surge of cheerfulness, his mood rises or the emotional background is leveled. The smoker feels like his brain is working better. The body likes this positive effect. But after about 2 hours, half of the nicotine that enters the blood is destroyed, so with the formed dependence, there is a desire to smoke a new cigarette.

Psychological dependence on nicotine develops first. It is associated with the ritual of smoking and certain situations when there is a need for tobacco. At first it is a company in which most smokers, nervous tension, in which cigarettes are used to distract thoughts. Many men start smoking during military service when it is necessary to fill a long wait or a long break. Then tobacco use is associated with a cup of coffee, driving a car and other situations.

At the stage of psychological dependence, there is still no acute need for nicotine, the process itself is important. Narcologists call this stereotypical behavior. Therefore, a person can easily quit smoking and not experience withdrawal if they manage to break the psychological model.

Special conditions are necessary to start smoking and form an addiction. Some researchers believe that the cause of a bad habit is heredity. 50% of children from families where parents smoke also become addicted. In non-smoking families, a bad habit appears in 25% of children. But this feature indicates more memorization of adult behavior patterns and greater availability of cigarettes.

With physical dependence, resistance to nicotine is formed. This manifests itself as a lack of euphoria and relaxation after smoking. Therefore, a person gradually increases the number of cigarettes smoked per day. The habit includes smoking immediately after waking up, on an empty stomach, after eating. The intervals between smoked cigarettes are shortened to 1-2 hours. If it is not possible to do this, then the following signs appear:

- feeling anxious and anxious;
- increased irritability;
- dysphoria;
- an uncontrollable desire to smoke;
- difficult concentration of attention;
- headache;
- increased appetite.

When contacting a specialist to get rid of smoking, the doctor determines the severity of the condition according to certain symptoms. It is necessary to answer questions about the number of cigarettes smoked per day, smoking after waking up and the total length of tobacco use. The more a person depends on tobacco, the longer the treatment takes and the higher the risk of a breakdown.

To get rid of the signs of addiction, it is recommended to consult a doctor. Without special medical care, only 5% of people manage to overcome a bad habit, and with the treatment of specialists, remission for 3 years or more is achieved in 25%.

In relation to our country, this problem is particularly relevant and its roots go deep into the history of our people, and its spread is also associated with the low culture of society. Not only society should fight this problem, but also everyone should be aware of the great harm of smoking for themselves and try to fight it.

More and more of my friends and acquaintances are drawn into this habit. Many people can no longer imagine their life without a cigarette. It became interesting to me what is the prevalence of smoking among young people in the lyceum and in general in other countries of the world. I was also interested in the impact of smoking not only on the health of a young smoker, but also on the health of his future children. In addition, smoking also harms the country's economy, which has also become the object of research.

1-2 packs of cigarettes contain a lethal dose of nicotine. The smoker is saved by the fact that this dose is injected into the body not immediately, but fractional. The statistics say: compared with non-smokers, long-term smokers are 13 times more likely to develop Angina pectoris, 12 times - Myocardial infarction, 10 times - Stomach ulcer. Smokers make up 96-100% of all lung cancer patients. Every seventh smoker for a long time suffers from Obliterating endarteritis - a serious ailment of blood vessels.

Tobacco products are prepared from dried tobacco leaves, which contain proteins, carbohydrates, mineral salts, fiber, enzymes, fatty acids and others. Among them, it is important to note two groups of substances dangerous to humans - nicotine and isoprenoids.

Nicotine also affects the endocrine glands, in particular the adrenal glands, which at the same time secrete harmon - Adrenaline into the blood, causing

vasospasm, increased blood pressure and increased heart rate. Adversely affecting the sex glands, nicotine contributes to the development of sexual weakness in men - impotence! Therefore, her treatment begins with the fact that the patient is offered to stop smoking.

Smoking is especially harmful for children and adolescents. The nervous and circulatory systems that are not yet strong react painfully to tobacco.

In addition to nicotine, other components of tobacco smoke also have a negative effect. When carbon monoxide enters the body, oxygen starvation develops, due to the fact that carbon monoxide combines more easily with hemoglobin than oxygen and is delivered with blood to all human tissues and organs. The statistics say: compared with non-smokers, long-term smokers are 13 times more likely to suffer from heart disease, 10 times more likely to suffer from stomach ulcers. Smokers make up 96-100% of all lung cancer patients. Every seventh smoker has been ill for a long time - a serious ailment of blood vessels.

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In the experiment, it was found that 70% of mice who inhaled tobacco smoke developed malignant lung tumors. Cancer in smokers occurs 20 times more often than in non-smokers. The longer a person smokes, the more likely he is to die from

this serious disease. Smokers often have cancer of the lower lip as a result of the carcinogenic effect of the extract accumulating in the mouthpiece of the tube.

The absorption of nicotine in the body depends on the pH levels at its intake. The absorption of nicotine from acidic cigarette smoke occurs in the lungs. Alkaline tobacco smoke from pipes and cigars allows nicotine to be absorbed through the mucous membrane in the mouth. Smokeless tobacco products and nicotine gum (a means to stop smoking) are prepared in a special way to facilitate oral absorption. Absorption through the lungs is faster. From the lungs, nicotine quickly enters the blood and brain. Nicotine acts through special cellular formations, or receptors, located at the junctions of nerve cells, or synapses, in the brain and muscle tissue. These receptors have the ability to recognize nicotine and respond to it when it is present in the body. As a result, the work of the synapse changes, that is, the transmission of a nerve impulse that controls the state of blood vessels, muscle tissue, glands of external or internal secretion is distorted. When the receptors signal the presence of nicotine, blood pressure increases and peripheral circulation slows down. The waves in the brain change, and a number of endocrine and metabolic effects are triggered.

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